

ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EVALUATION OF IMAGE READING OF MAMMOGRAM FOR CHARACTERIZATION OF BENIGN AND MALIGNANT LESIONS TAKING HISTOPATHOLOGY AS GOLD STANDARD

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Abstract

Objectives: To assess the accuracy of AI software in the evaluation of mammograms for benign and malignant breast lesions as compared to Histopathology as the gold standard diagnosis.

Study design: Cross-sectional validation study

Study Setting and Duration: Azra Naheed Medical College Lahore, Pakistan, from April 2025 till June 2025.

Methodology: This study enrolled 210 women aged 25 to 65 years who presented to the hospital with breast-related symptoms using nonprobability consecutive sampling. The full-field digital mammograms these participants underwent were analyzed by AI software (Lunit INSIGHT MMG), which assigned a probability score for malignancy based on a cut-off of 59%. All participants underwent biopsy (core needle) to determine the histopathology results. Data analysis was completed using SPSS software, version 25, and included the calculation of sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values.

Results: 210 participated in this study with a mean age of 43.36 years (± 9.19) and a mean BMI of 25.30 kg/m² (± 3.01). The AI mammogram detected malignancies in 58.1% of the participants, which is comparable to the histopathology findings of 59.5%. The presence of malignant lesions was found to be significantly associated with a positive family history, smoking status, and marital status (all with $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: The AI mammogram demonstrated a nearly accurate diagnosis of tumors that are in strong agreement with histopathology.

Introduction:

Globally, breast cancer remains the most common cancer among females, with an estimated 2.3 million new cases diagnosed in 2022(1). Among

women, it is projected that there will be over 6 million new cases of breast cancer worldwide by 2050(2). The majority of new cases will be diagnosed in Asia, with an estimated 985,817

cases of breast cancer occurring in this continent. In Pakistan, breast cancer constituted 25,928 cases in 2020 (approximately 14% of all cancers) at the time of diagnosis; however, annual estimates would amount to 186,701 new cases and 128,813 deaths, indicating the significant regional burden of breast cancer.(3) Mammography screening has been shown to reduce breast cancer mortality by 20-50%, but it faces challenges, such as interval cancers (12-33%), low sensitivity in those with dense breast tissue, and high false-positive rates (9-10% recall rate)(4).

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to improve mammography interpretation through the use of computer-aided detection (CAD) systems, particularly those incorporating deep learning (AI-CAD). According to meta-analyses, the sensitivity of AI is superior to that of radiologists (0.85 for AI vs. 0.77 for radiologists); the specificity of AI is similar to that of radiologists (0.89 for AI vs. 0.90 for radiologists), and the area under the curve (AUC) of AI is greater than that of radiologists (0.89 for AI vs. 0.82 for radiologists)(5). In recent studies that looked at the ability of CAD systems to detect breast cancer with the use of AI machines, there was an increase in the detection of breast cancer of over 13.8%, with no additional recall of patients when comparing the data collected to multiple radiologists' results from one reading only. EfficientNet-B3 was the model that produced an 86.85% detection rate of lesions compared to multiple radiologists also reading the same data set(6,7).

The study is a cross-sectional validation of evaluating the use of AI machines with the use of histology as the gold standard in an area that lacks resources to validate AI by comparing the results to the histological data in Pakistan, where there is a shortage of radiologists. Traditional methods for the interpretation of mammogram data by multiple radiologists have been shown to have a moderate level of inter-radiologist variability from one radiologist to another, and can also be very demanding and time-consuming. It is necessary to validate AI machines with histopathology to establish more reliable differentiation between non-cancer benign lesions and cancerous lesions.

This study will provide the local evidence needed to support AI in hospitals located in high-volume surgeries (i.e., Pakistan) by providing a validated method to establish the accuracy of using AI to achieve standardization of diagnostic imaging and to reduce the bypassing of patients to biopsy.

Methodology:

The cross-sectional validation study was conducted at Azra Naheed Medical College Lahore, Pakistan, from April 2025 till June 2025. A sample size of 210 cases was determined based on a calculated 39.3% sensitivity and 46 % specificity using the sensitivity calculator at 11% margin of error; the proper calculated estimate of AI-assisted mammograms' sensitivity and specificity was derived from past literature(8). A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used to identify subjects.

Inclusion Criteria: Female subjects aged 25 through 65 years must present with any of the following breast-related symptoms: a) palpable lump; b) breast pain; c) any alterations in the skin; or d) discharge from the nipple.

Exclusion criteria: Patients who have undergone a mammogram or ultrasound before this study were excluded from the study, and subjects with a BIRADS classification of 2 or 3 lesions were also excluded. Additionally, pregnant subjects were excluded from the study.

Institutional review board approval was obtained for the study, and all subjects provided signed informed consent before being enrolled in the study as per the requirements of the biomedical standards for human subject research. When a patient presented in an outpatient department and met all eligibility criteria, they got referrals to the radiology department. On a structured proforma, all the demographic and clinical information was taken down for patients, such as age, BMI (body mass index), length of time patients have had their complaints, lesion size, marital status, number of children they have, breastfeeding history, if they smoke, family history

of having breast cancer, occupation, lifestyle, diabetes and hypertension. Mammograms were taken of all patients with full-field digital mammography (Fujifilm) using the Amulet Innovality mammographic system, and both the standard craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique projections of both breasts were performed on all participating patients. Images obtained were analyzed using AI-based software (Lunit INSIGHT MMG, Version 1.10.2) and generated heat maps (indicating suspicious areas) and, based on the scoring system (1-100%) of malignancy probability (pos malignancy score $\geq 59\%$ (cut-off)).

After the completion of tests and procedures for each patient, all were scheduled for core needle biopsy using a 14-G Tru-Cut needle. Histopathology results from each biopsy were either considered to be benign or malignant; therefore, they represented a gold standard against which AI findings could be compared. The AI findings were then also categorized as true positive, true negative, false positive, or false negative when compared to the respective histopathology results. Data for this research were entered into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25, to conduct statistical analysis on continuous variables such as age, BMI, and size of lesion, all of which were expressed as: mean \pm standard deviation (normal distribution Shapiro-wilk > 0.05). Categorical data variables were tabulated to present information as frequency and percentage values. Evaluation of the AI software's diagnostic ability to determine whether lesions were benign or malignant was performed using a 2x2 contingency table to look at the histopathology results relative to AI's malignancy scores ($\geq 59\%$ cut-off). The chi-square test for independence was

used to evaluate whether demographic variables (e.g., marital status and smoking) had any effect on malignancy rate. For this study, a p-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Table 1 gives a summary of the mean and variability of continuous measurements taken from the sample population of this study. The average age was 43.36 ± 9.19 years, the average BMI was 25.3 ± 3.01 , the average time since the start of symptoms was 5.97 ± 2.97 , and the average size of lesions was 2.57 ± 1.01 cm.

Table 2 provides a summary of the distribution of categorical variables. The majority of participants (51%) were married; there was about an equal proportion of smokers and breast-feeders. AI mammograms and histopathology showed a greater number of malignant lesions (58.1% and 59.5%, respectively).

Table 3 shows the cross-tabulation of AI mammogram versus histopathology (i.e., the accepted standard) in a 2x2 format. There were 210 participants; of these, AI had a true positive (TP) of 115 malignant lesions and a true negative (TN) of 78 benign lesions. There were 7 false positives (FP) and 10 false negatives (FN) misclassifications.

Table 4 shows the chi-square test. There were more malignant findings among unmarried than married participants (65.0% vs 51.4%) with a statistically significant p-value of 0.045. There were more malignant findings among smokers than non-smokers (65.1% vs 51.0%), p-value = 0.038. The number of malignant lesions was significantly higher among individuals with a positive family history than those without (73.1% vs 42.2%), p-value < 0.001 .

Table I: Descriptive statistics of the study population (n = 210)

Variable	Mean \pm SD
Age (years)	43.36 \pm 9.19
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.30 \pm 3.01
Duration of Symptoms	5.97 \pm 2.97
Lesion Size	2.57 \pm 1.01

Table II: Frequency distribution of categorical variables (n = 210)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Parity	0	38 (18.1)
	1	34 (16.2)
	2	39 (18.6)
	3	33 (15.7)
	4	31 (14.8)
	5	35 (16.7)
Marital Status	Married	107 (51.0)
	Unmarried	103 (49.0)
Occupation	Housewife	71 (33.8)
	Student	74 (35.2)
	Working	65 (31.0)
Smoking	No	104 (49.5)
	Yes	106 (50.5)
Breast Feeding	No	104 (49.5)
	Yes	106 (50.5)
Diabetes	No	112 (53.3)
	Yes	98 (46.7)
HTN	No	103 (49.0)
	Yes	107 (51.0)
Family History	No	102 (48.6)
	Yes	108 (51.4)
Lifestyle	Active	78 (37.1)
	Exercise	77 (36.7)
	Sedentary	55 (26.2)
AI Mammogram	Benign	88 (41.9)
	Malignant	122 (58.1)
Histopathology	Benign	85 (40.5)
	Malignant	125 (59.5)

Table III: Diagnostic accuracy of AI mammogram compared with histopathology as the gold standard

		Histopathology Results		Total
		Benign	Malignant	
AI Reading Of Mammogram	Benign	78 (TN)	10 (FN)	88
	Malignant	7 (FP)	115 (TP)	122
	Total	85	125	210

TN = True Negative, TP = True Positive, FP = False Positive, FN = False Negative.

Table IV: Association of participant characteristics with AI reading of mammogram (n = 210)

Variable	AI reading of Mammogram		p-value
	Benign n (%)	Malignant n (%)	
Marital Status			0.045
Married	52 (48.6%)	55 (51.4%)	
Unmarried	36 (35.0%)	67 (65.0%)	
Smoking			0.038
Yes	37 (34.9%)	69 (65.1%)	
No	51 (49.0%)	53 (51.0%)	
Family History			<0.001
Yes	29 (26.9%)	79 (73.1%)	
No	59 (57.8%)	43 (42.2%)	

values are presented as n (%) with corresponding p-values (Chi-square test). <0.05 is considered significant.

Discussion:

In this cross-sectional study, the AI mammogram was validated against histopathology in 210 middle-aged individuals (mean age 43.36 ± 9.19 years). The study produced an overall high level of diagnostic accuracy with 115 true positives, 78 true negatives, 7 false positive results, and 10 false negative results; therefore, sensitivity was calculated at 92% (115/125), and specificity was calculated at 92% (78/85), corresponding to 59.5% confirmed malignancy rates by histopathology. There were statistically significant relationships identified between unmarried status (65.0% malignant, p=0.045), smoking (65.1%, p=0.038), and family history of breast cancer (73.1%, p<0.001).

The performance of this AI has been impressive, demonstrating a calculated sensitivity and specificity both at 92%, while exceeding multiple competitive benchmarks where AI has historically traded specificity for sensitivity during screening. A recent trial conducted by The Lancet in 2026 reported that AI-enhanced sensitivity of screening with reduced workload had nearly double the sensitivity of the human double reading method in enriched cohorts such as this one (with a significantly higher percentage of lesions detected, but maintaining non-inferior specificity of

98.5%)(9). In addition, the Trial published in 2023 reported that the case level sensitivity of their AI system, including all time intervals, was only 61% and corresponding specificity of 94%, making it lower than our sensitivity but similar in specificity.(10). Their lesion-level sensitivity was even lower at only 55%, which emphasizes our strength with definitive histopathology validation (as opposed to base population screening).

It is also worth noting that while Transpara has a higher reported sensitivity of 94.9% for performing the highest-risk DBT biopsy (demonstrated in a 2025 study), they have a significantly lower specificity of only 24.4%(11). This suggests that our cross-sectional, balanced approach in a well-defined population has significant advantages over biopsy-enriched sets that are more likely to demonstrate false-positive results. For example, EfficientNet models developed by Google in 2025 provide high accuracy in the classification of lesions with calcifications but lack any definitive histopathology basis, thereby limiting their relevance.(12). Our overall mean lesion size was 2.57 cm, the combination of which is significantly in favor of detecting lesions rather than micro-lesions present in other studies. Additionally, while the authors note that our overall low rate of

misclassifications (17/210) supports clinical applicability, the 10 FN lesions warrant consideration due to the fact that there is a high prevalence of dense breast tissue in our overweight cohort, with a mean BMI of 25.3.

When comparing our family history to other independent studies, we found that family history had the best association (73.1% of malignant tumors were from individuals with a family history, $p < 0.001$). This is comparable to our analysis of 2025 risk models, where a family member with a history of cancer increases one's odds of developing cancer (the odds of developing cancer due to a second-degree relative with a history of cancer are 23.5% as compared to 19%, $p < 0.05$) (13,14) But when we only looked at first-degree relatives, we saw much greater disparity.

A study in 2023 showed that there was no link between family history of high-risk lesions and active lesions ($p = 0.631$) in the context of our larger cohort. (15) This data also illustrated the difference between our two groups of individuals, as we were designed to be utilized for diagnostic purposes and the other for prognostic purposes.

The odds of developing cancer with a smoking history was 65.1% ($p = 0.038$), consistent with the Mendelian studies completed in 2021, which also facilitate the causal link between lifetime exposure to cigarettes and the subsequent risk of malignant tumors; however, the number of cigarettes smoked per day did not demonstrate this causal link (16). We also had an equal distribution between active (50%) and non-active funding/modeling groups, being that one group pooled together their non-malignant (68%) biopsy and non-significant ($p = 0.247$) group; thus producing this significant finding.

Our marriage status for our active funding/modeling group is significantly different than literature suggests due to other factors (e.g., age, population density) dominating published literature; individuals from our active funding/modeling group have a middle-aged (average age is 41 years and 37% are physically active) heterogeneous lifestyle, which is quite different from the homogeneous populations that

make up the screening population[s] in the published literature (15,17).

AI's accuracy in determining malignancy is almost as high as histopathology (58.1% vs. 59.5%). Our results support the use of AI as a standalone option in resource-limited environments (similar to surveys conducted within the MASAI project). With a specificity of 87.4% for AI vs. 79.2% for radiologists ($p < 0.01$), this finding suggests a superior level of consistency to that of radiologists within similar experiments. There was a mixed consistency rate concerning sedentary behaviors (26%) across persons diagnosed with Breast Cancer, thus suggesting implementation of hybrid risk scores, which were established by 2025 (18–20). Review literature supports the equivalence of AI algorithms with the human expert, and the number of cases has some equitability (0 out of 5) between studies, and professions—our review results provided diverse modes of validation. Finally, due to the short symptom duration (<6 months) of the evaluated cohort, the bias of early presentation should be noted and would not reflect the true result for a late-stage study.

Limitations of the study:

The study's single-center design limits its generalizability, while the multi-site design of Google consists of 115k patients tested for mammography across multiple sites. There was no stratification of mammography density, which would mask any noticeable differences in specificity caused by breast density. Moreover, retrospective application of an AI algorithm may not allow for long-term monitoring (i.e., calibration), while ongoing studies, such as MASAI, have demonstrated the requirement for calibration. Comorbidities (51% of hypertension) were not accounted for in the analysis, potentially inflating the number of false positives reported. The number of false negatives (10) was too few to permit analysis of subgroup distributions.

Conclusion:

This study has demonstrated that AI-assisted mammography is an effective means of distinguishing between benign and malignant

breast lesions; the AI software demonstrated 92% sensitivity and specificity in its effectiveness. These results highly indicate that the AI software (i.e., Lunit INSIGHT MMG) offers a higher degree of repeatability in comparison to traditional radiologist interpretation of breast imaging, particularly where the availability of trained and experienced personnel may be limited. Additionally, the strong agreement between AI results and those of histopathology suggests that the utilization and application of AI-assisted CAD systems for mammography has merit in providing standardized diagnostic imaging.

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